

A Lightweight, Few-Shot Framework for Autonomous Morphology-Resolved SEM–EDS Analysis of Energy Materials

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Abstract

High-throughput (nano)materials characterization is a challenging aspect of the autonomous laboratory concept. Moreover, extracting statistically meaningful particle-level compositional information, such as heterogeneity or impurity, from Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) with co-acquired Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) remains fully manual, and expertise-intensive. Here, we established a deep learning-driven, lightweight, and data-efficient framework for direct integration into SEM–EDS characterization workflows, enabling rapid, automated, morphology-resolved identification and compositional quantification. To overcome the major limitation of existing deep learning-based methods that rely on large, annotated datasets and time-consuming human power, our framework operates with minimal human labeling. With only five fully human-labeled SEM images, we generated a synthetic training dataset of approximately 12,000 labeled objects via a canvas-based synthetic data generation strategy. This enables a lightweight segmentation model to reach a mean Intersection-over-Union of 0.74 — a 12-percentage-point gain over the same model trained on the five labeled images alone, and up to 27 points with only two labeled images. Applied to MXene energy-storage materials, the framework links each class to its elemental composition through EDS maps and reveals impurity distributions hidden in conventional field-averaged analysis. In practice, the pipeline is designed as a deployable solution that integrates directly into existing SEM–EDS instrumentation without complex architectures or high-performance computing establishing an accessible pathway toward autonomous electron microscopy, lowering the barrier to widespread adoption of deep learning-driven materials characterization.

1 Introduction

In materials and energy storage research, diverse novel electrode materials have been developed, including the well-known two-dimensional (2D) MXene materials¹. Their tunable compositions, surface terminations, and layered structures enable diverse physicochemical properties. These features make them attractive for applications in energy storage, semiconductors, catalysis, and sensing². These advantages have driven growing demand and motivated efforts to scale up production. However, upscaling of MXene requires rigorous quality control, since contaminants, undesired byproducts, and oxide residues can degrade bulk performance, and stability of the material such as active site blockage³. In battery research, visualizing the elemental distribution across the electrode surface before and after battery cycling can reveal material performance, degradation products, and local active sites⁴. Therefore, it is essential to precisely determine the distribution of the raw materials and contaminants in MXene samples to advance research and accelerate innovation.

Standard characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) face inherent trade-offs in quantifying composition and impurities across length scales. They typically capture either bulk-averaged signals or nanoscale features, but rarely both quantitatively⁵.

To precisely analyze the material structure and composition at the micro- to nanoscale, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is a widely adopted characterization technique in materials science, providing complementary high-resolution images of micro- to nano-structural features. Sometimes, SEM reveals distinct contrast within composite materials, suggesting a multiphase nature. When coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), it provides an elemental distribution map at a single point or across the area of interest. This technique detects X-rays emitted by each element in the sample (in counts) after irradiation with the electron beam and provides an EDS spectrum (counts vs. keV) for each element, with characteristic peaks that serve as a fingerprint^{6,7}. While SEM provides information on morphology and phase boundaries, EDS reveals the elemental composition, such as carbon (C), oxygen (O), fluorine (F), aluminum (Al), and titanium (Ti), on the MXene surface; see Figure 1. This information can suggest the material stoichiometry or phase compositions based on the EDS distribution in atomic and weight percentages. EDS analysis essentially involves quantitative analysis to determine the relative concentration of elements within a sample, such as chip/semiconductor or battery manufacturing and pharmaceutical production, to ensure proper yield⁸, performance, quality, and standard control. This combination directly links morphological features to local elemental composition, enabling phase identification, stoichiometry quantification⁷, and mapping of contaminant or phase distributions within the composite material⁹, which is crucial for understanding battery behavior both at nanoscopic and bulk view. These capabilities are critical for quality control not limited to only battery research field, but also chip and semiconductor¹⁰, and high-value material manufacturing applications.

Despite these strengths, conventional SEM–EDS analysis relies on manual operation and expert interpretation. Surveying particles across multiple regions is time- and resource-intensive, limiting throughput and reproducibility for large-scale quality control.

To keep pace with rapid materials development in the era of big data and automation, the field is moving toward efficient, automated characterization workflows with minimal human intervention. Recent advances have introduced deep learning (DL) for automated feature extraction from microscopy images¹¹⁻¹⁷. However, most existing models require extensive manual annotation of regions of interest (ROIs) and large training sets, limiting their practicality and risking overfitting on small datasets. Moreover, the automated, morphology-resolved correlation between SEM-detected features and co-acquired EDS elemental maps remains largely unexplored.

To overcome these critical bottlenecks, we develop a lightweight, data-efficient framework that couples deep learning–based morphology segmentation of SEM images with mask-guided EDS analysis, enabling automated, morphology-resolved compositional quantification (Figure 1). To overcome data scarcity, we introduce realistic synthetic SEM data generated using the a canvas-based synthetic data generation strategy rather than Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)¹⁸, which are commonly used to simulate synthetic SEM images, however often limited by their computational cost and the need for large datasets. The canvas-based strategy^{19,20} generates entirely new synthetic micrographs — composing mosaic backgrounds from sub-patches and populating them with instances from a curated morphology pool. Unlike

standard copy-paste augmentation²¹, which pastes instances onto existing training images, our approach produces fully synthetic training images in which class ratio and object density can be specified independently.

As demonstrated in complex SEM micrographs of MXenes, the framework achieves rapid segmentation and quantitative phase analysis with minimal manual labeling and computational resources. Our segmentation model (15M parameters) runs efficiently on standard CPUs at ~1.3 seconds per image, enabling direct deployment on existing SEM workstations without dedicated GPU hardware or external inference servers. Ultimately, this work offers the AI-driven semiautomated SEM-EDS platform “SEMEX.Lab” that simplifies the analysis of compositional heterogeneity and advances accessible, deployable AI-driven materials characterization.

Figure 1. Conventional SEM-EDS workflow versus the proposed AI-driven automated morphology–phase analysis. (a) *In the conventional workflow*, an expert manually selects regions of interest, inspects features, and correlates SEM morphology with EDS elemental maps (e.g., Ti, F). The output is a single field-averaged elemental composition, with no breakdown by particle morphology. The analysis typically takes hours per sample. (b) *In the proposed workflow*, a segmentation model — trained on a small set of annotated SEM images together with synthetic data — takes SEM images and co-acquired EDS maps as input and performs inference in ~1.3 seconds on a standard CPU and 34ms on GPU. Implemented in

SEMEX.Lab, it segments morphological classes (Flake, Sphere, Other). For each class, it reports stoichiometry and population statistics.

2 Results

We present a SEM–EDS analysis framework that takes unlabeled SEM micrographs and co-acquired EDS maps as input and produces morphology-resolved compositional statistics. A canvas-based strategy expands a handful of labeled images into a synthetic training set, a lightweight segmentation model trained on this set assigns each pixel to a morphology class, and the predicted masks are then intersected with EDS maps to recover per-morphology elemental composition. The framework was developed using an SEM dataset of 2D energy-storage materials, acquired under consistent imaging conditions via high-throughput automated SEM, with co-acquired EDS elemental maps for selected regions of interest. A fixed set of 70 manually annotated images, containing 12,486 morphological objects, was held out for validation and testing. For training, we deliberately varied the number of manually annotated SEM images from 0 to 10 to probe the framework's behavior in the low-data regime.

To enable training in this low-data regime, we generated a synthetic dataset (D') using the canvas-based strategy to augment the real annotated images D . (*Section 2.1*). We first evaluated segmentation performance by comparing models trained on real data alone (D) against those trained on real and synthetic data ($D \cup D'$) (*Section 2.2*). We then assessed model robustness under varying training conditions: initial real image count, synthetic image count, objects per synthetic image, and class ratio (*Section 2.3*). Finally, we performed qualitative and quantitative morphology-resolved EDS analysis using the segmented SEM masks to link morphological classes to their elemental composition (*Section 2.4*).

2.1 Segmentation pipeline with synthetic training data

Training semantic segmentation models typically requires hundreds or thousands of manually annotated images, a significant barrier for materials-science applications. Our pipeline reduces this requirement to as few as 5 labeled images, combined with synthetic data generated by the canvas-based strategy.

Our segmentation pipeline consists of three stages, summarized in Figure 2. First, high-throughput SEM acquisition produces a large pool of unlabeled micrographs of the target energy-material samples. An expert annotator selects a small subset — between zero and ten images in the experiments reported below — and provides pixel-level labels. Each object is assigned to one of three morphology classes: Flake, Sphere, or Other, forming the labeled dataset D (Figure 2a). Second, we extract the labeled objects from D using its segmentation mask, organizing them into a per-class morphology pool. For each synthetic image, a new background is constructed by tiling 10×10 pixels random crops drawn from the background regions of D in a mosaic pattern until a 1024×1024 pixels canvas is filled. Objects are then sampled from the morphology pool and pasted onto this background at random positions, producing a set of fully labeled synthetic images D' (Figure 2b). When objects overlap, they are layered in a fixed order — Flake at the bottom, Sphere in the middle, Other on top — so that rarer morphologies remain visible above more common ones. Third, a segmentation model is trained on the union of the labeled images D and the synthetic set D' (Figure 2c). Figure 3 compares representative synthetic images with real SEM micrographs, showing

close visual similarity across the three morphology classes. At inference, the trained model segments unlabeled SEM images in ~ 1.3 seconds per image on a standard CPU and ~ 35 ms on an RTX 3090 GPU. The resulting masks feed into the downstream morphology-resolved EDS analysis described in *Section 2.4* (Figure 6). Full implementation details for each stage are given in Methods (*Section 4.3*)

Figure 2. Overview of the automated, morphology-resolved SEM characterization pipeline. (a) *Data acquisition and annotation.* SEM images are acquired under consistent imaging conditions (see Section 4); a small representative subset (~ 5 images) is selected and pixel-level annotated by a human expert into three morphology classes — Flake (blue), Sphere (purple), and Other (orange) — yielding the labeled dataset D . (b) *Synthetic data generation.* Object instances are extracted from D to build a per-class morphology pool. In parallel, 10×10 pixel patches are sampled from the background regions of D and tiled in a mosaic pattern to construct a 1024×1024 pixel canvas. Objects from the morphology pool are randomly placed onto the canvas, producing the synthetic dataset D' . (c) *Model training and inference.* The combined dataset ($D \cup D'$) is used to train the segmentation model M_{seg} , which produces pixel-wise semantic masks at inference (~ 34 ms per image on a consumer GPU; ~ 1.3 seconds on a standard CPU).

Figure 3. Comparison of real and synthetic SEM training images. (a) Representative real SEM image from the labeled dataset D , with overlaid morphology classes: Flake (blue), Other (orange), and Sphere (purple). (b) Representative synthetic image generated by the canvas-based strategy (D'), shown with the same overlay scheme. (c) Magnified per-class crops of representative objects from D (left) and D' (right) for each morphology class (Flake, Other, Sphere). Additional examples are provided in Supplementary Figure S4.

2.2 Synthetic data improves segmentation with minimal labeled examples

We first evaluated whether training with synthetic data D' alongside real labeled D data improves segmentation performance. We trained a UNet++²² model on $D \cup D'$ and compared it with the same architecture trained on D alone. The choice of the number of real labeled images ($|D| = 5$) and synthetic images ($|D'| = 100$) is justified by the ablation study in *Section 2.3*; here, we use these settings to first establish the overall benefit of synthetic data. To ensure a fair comparison, we performed three independent runs with different random seeds — covering synthetic dataset generation, model training, and inference — while keeping the validation and test sets fixed across all runs. The model trained with $D \cup D'$ achieved a mean Intersection-over-Union (mIoU) of 0.743 ± 0.003 compared with 0.623 ± 0.039 for the baseline trained on D alone, and a mean Dice coefficient of 0.845 ± 0.002 compared with 0.727 ± 0.061 — an absolute improvement of approximately 12 percentage points (pp) in both metrics (Table 1).

The benefit of synthetic data is highly non-uniform across morphology classes. The Flake class gains only +2.7 pp in IoU ($0.714 \rightarrow 0.741$) and +1.8 pp in Dice. This modest improvement reflects the dominance of

flakes in the source data: the instance pool extracted from D contains 473 Flakes compared to 89 Spheres and 15 Other particles — a roughly 32:6:1 ratio. Even five real images therefore expose the model to abundant flake instances and flake boundary pixels, placing the baseline trained on D alone close to the achievable performance ceiling for this class and leaving little headroom for synthetic data to contribute. In contrast, the Sphere class gains +15.0 pp in IoU (0.530 \rightarrow 0.680) and the Other class gains +29.5 pp (0.293 \rightarrow 0.588), with parallel trends in Dice (+11.9 pp and +33.3 pp, respectively).

Figure 4 shows qualitative comparisons between the model trained with D and with $D \cup D'$ on five representative test images. The model trained with D frequently misclassifies small spherical particles and irregular fragments, particularly in dense regions (Figure 4c, red arrows), while the model trained with $D \cup D'$ correctly recovers these structures (Figure 4c, green arrows) and produces more coherent boundaries even in flake-dominated images (Figure 4a). The model trained with $D \cup D'$ is also markedly more reproducible across runs: the standard deviation of the Other-class IoU drops from 0.206 to 0.013 — over an order of magnitude — and the standard deviation of mIoU drops from 0.039 to 0.003. Such variance reduction is critical for practical deployment, where users need confidence that a model trained on a handful of labeled images will behave consistently across runs. Having established that synthetic data substantially improves both accuracy and stability at $|D| = 5$, we next examine how this benefit depends on the choice of synthetic data generation parameters.

To confirm that these gains stem from the canvas-based design rather than from synthetic data generation in general, we also compared against standard geometric and photometric augmentation applied to the same five real images. The canvas pipeline outperformed this augmentation-only baseline by +18.1 pp mIoU (Supplementary Note 3).

Table 1. Adding synthetic data improves segmentation, with the largest gains for under-represented classes. Performance of UNet++ trained on (i) real annotated SEM images only (D , $|D|=5$) versus (ii) real images combined with synthetic images ($D \cup D'$), $|D'| = 100$, $k = 120$ objects per image, Flake:Sphere:Other = 1:1:1; parameter choices justified in *Section 2.3*, evaluated on a held-out test set of 35 images (4,865 annotated objects). (a) Per-class and mean Intersection-over-Union. (b) Per-class and mean Dice coefficient. mIoU and mDice are averaged over the four classes (Flake, Sphere, Other, Background). Values are mean \pm s.d. across three independent training runs. Δ (pp) denotes the absolute improvement of (ii) over (i) in percentage points.

(a) Intersection-over-Union					
Training regime	mIoU	IoU Flake	IoU Sphere	IoU Other	IoU Background
Real only (D)	0.623 \pm 0.039	0.714 \pm 0.003	0.530 \pm 0.052	0.293 \pm 0.206	0.956 \pm 0.001
Real + Synthetic ($D \cup D'$)	0.743 \pm 0.003	0.741 \pm 0.006	0.680 \pm 0.007	0.588 \pm 0.013	0.961 \pm 0.001
Δ (pp)	+12.0	+2.7	+15.0	+29.5	+0.5
(b) Dice coefficient					
Training regime	mDice	Dice Flake	Dice Sphere	Dice Other	Dice Background
Real only (D)	0.727 \pm 0.061	0.833 \pm 0.002	0.691 \pm 0.043	0.407 \pm 0.287	0.977 \pm 0.001
Real + Synthetic ($D \cup D'$)	0.845 \pm 0.002	0.851 \pm 0.004	0.810 \pm 0.005	0.740 \pm 0.010	0.980 \pm 0.001
Δ (pp)	+11.8	+1.8	+11.9	+33.3	+0.3

Figure 4. Qualitative comparison of segmentation results. Columns (left to right): original SEM image, expert ground-truth annotation, prediction from the model trained on real data only (D), and prediction from the model trained on real data combined with synthetic data ($D \cup D'$). Per-image mIoU is reported in the top-left corner of each prediction panel. Segmentation masks are color-coded by morphology class: Flake (blue), Sphere (purple), and Other (orange). Red arrows indicate misclassified regions from the model trained with D prediction; green arrows indicate the corresponding regions correctly segmented from the model trained with $D \cup D'$ prediction. Rows show three representative scenarios of increasing difficulty: (a) a field dominated by a single large flake; (b) a sparse field of mixed Flakes, Spheres, and Other particles; (c) a dense field of small particles spanning all three morphology classes.

2.3 Ablation study of the synthetic data generation pipeline

To identify the conditions under which the synthetic data pipeline is most effective, we systematically varied four generation parameters: (Q1) the number of real labeled images $|D|$, (Q2) the number of synthetic images $|D'|$, (Q3) the number of objects packed into each synthetic image (k), and (Q4) the class ratio among Flakes, Spheres, and Others. Default values and tested ranges for all generation parameters are

summarize in Table S2; full numerical results for each ablation are listed in Tables S4–S7. The quantitative answers reported below are specific to our SEM imaging conditions and target morphologies; while we expect the qualitative trends to transfer to other particle-like SEM datasets, this remains to be verified. All experiments used three independent random seeds and were evaluated on the same held-out test set. The effects of 2D rotation augmentation and background canvas size are analyzed in Supplementary Notes 1 and 2.

(Q1) How many real labeled images are needed? We varied $|D|$ from 1 to 10 and trained the segmentation model on the combined dataset $|D \cup D'|$ (Figure 5a). Performance rises sharply between 1 and 5 real labeled images, from an mIoU of 0.475 ± 0.010 to 0.743 ± 0.003 , and plateaus thereafter in the range 0.743–0.768 up to $|D| = 10$. The gain is largest at $|D| = 2$ (+27 pp mIoU), confirming that the pipeline extracts useful diversity even from minimal labeled input. Together, these results indicate that the morphology pool saturates quickly and that a small number of well-chosen real images capture most of the morphological variability of the sample. We therefore fix $|D| = 5$ for all subsequent experiments: it is the smallest value at which performance saturates and corresponds to approximately 2.5 hours of expert annotation — a labeling budget compatible with routine SEM workflows.

(Q2) How many synthetic images are needed? Having fixed $|D| = 5$, we next asked whether the synthetic set D' itself saturates. We varied $|D'| \in \{50, 100, 150, 200, 300, 400, 500\}$ and trained the segmentation model on $D \cup D'$. Increasing $|D'|$ from 50 to 100 raised mean mIoU from 0.699 ± 0.043 to 0.743 ± 0.003 and reduced run-to-run standard deviation by over an order of magnitude (Figure 5b), indicating that fewer than ~ 100 synthetic images fail to cover the variation needed for stable training. Beyond this point, mean mIoU stabilized in the range 0.719–0.749 up to $|D'| = 500$. The largest single-step gain therefore occurs between 50 and 100 synthetic images (+4.4 pp mIoU, $\sim 14\times$ variance reduction). We therefore fix $|D'| = 100$ as the default in all subsequent experiments.

The plateau in mIoU beyond $|D'| = 100$ reflects a diversity ceiling inherited from D . Both the morphology pool and the mosaic backgrounds are derived from D — the pool by extracting labeled instances, the backgrounds by tiling 10×10 pixel patches from unannotated regions — so the effective diversity of D' is bounded by the content of D . Once $|D'|$ is large enough to span the combinatorial space of instance placements and background crops, further synthetic images only reshuffle the same source content and contribute no new morphological information. The relevant axis for further scaling is therefore the diversity of D , not the size of D' .

(Q3) How densely should objects be packed into each synthetic image? Holding all other generation parameters fixed, we varied the objects-per-image count $k \in \{10, 30, 60, 120, 300\}$. As shown in Figure 5c, performance rises sharply from mIoU = 0.394 ± 0.094 at $k = 10$ to 0.743 ± 0.003 at $k = 60$, and plateaus thereafter at $k = 120$.

We attribute the sharp gain at low k to the limited number of object instances and boundary pixels per image, which leaves the model with too few examples to learn from in each synthetic image. Once enough objects are present per image to provide a sufficient training signal, further increases in k no longer improve performance. Although $k = 60$ is already sufficient to saturate segmentation performance, we adopt $k = 120$ as the default because it matches the mean object density of our real SEM micrographs (~ 120 objects per 1024×1024 field).

(Q4) How should the class ratio be chosen? Fixing $k = 120$ and holding all other generation parameters at their defaults, we varied the Flake:Sphere:Other ratio across seven settings: 1:1:1, 3:1:1, 5:1:1, 1:3:1, 1:5:1, 1:1:3, and 1:1:5. Three models were trained per setting from independent random seeds.

Segmentation performance was largely insensitive to moderate Flake/Sphere imbalance: mIoU varied by less than 0.03 across the five settings 1:1:1, 3:1:1, 5:1:1, 1:3:1, and 1:5:1 (Figure 5d). In contrast, raising the Other ratio to 1:1:3 and 1:1:5 degraded mIoU from 0.751 (1:1:1 baseline) to 0.735 ± 0.016 and 0.716 ± 0.013 , respectively. We attribute this to the layering order described in Section 2.1: Other morphologies are pasted on top and therefore occlude any underlying Flake or Sphere pixels. At fixed k , increasing the Other fraction progressively covers the Flake and Sphere boundaries that carry informative learning signal, leaving less for the model to learn from.

Figure 5. Ablation of synthetic data generation parameters. (a) Effect of the number of real training images ($|D|$) on mIoU, comparing models trained on real data only (D) and on real data combined with synthetic data ($D \cup D'$). (b) Effect of the synthetic set size ($|D'|$) on mIoU, with $|D| = 5$. (c) Effect of the number of objects per synthetic image (k) on mIoU, with $|D| = 5$ and $|D'| = 100$. (d) Per-class IoU and mIoU across class ratios (Flake:Sphere:Other), grouped by over-represented class (*Baseline*, *Over-Flake*, *Over-Sphere*, *Over-Other*). Vertical dashed lines in (a–c) mark default settings; horizontal dashed lines in (b) and (c) mark the model trained on real data only (D). Shaded regions and error bars indicate the standard deviation across three independent runs.

2.4 Morphology-resolved elemental analysis

By integrating the segmentation mask with EDS elemental maps, the framework enables the extraction of particle-level compositional statistics that are inaccessible through conventional analysis. Rather than

functioning merely as a statistical data extraction tool, SEMEX.Lab user interface (UI) serves as an interpretive platform that enables a deep, physics-grounded understanding of material systems — including heterogeneous samples in which morphologically distinct particle populations may share the same elemental identity, or, conversely, in which particles of similar shape may belong to entirely different phases.

Figure 6. Workflow for morphology-resolved EDS analysis. (a) SEM–EDS acquisition produces an SEM image and co-acquired EDS elemental maps for six elements (Cl, O, Al, Ti, F, N). (b) The unlabeled SEM image is passed through the trained segmentation model M_{seg} (Section 2.2), which assigns every pixel to one of three morphology classes — Flake (blue), Sphere (purple), or Other (orange) — yielding a semantic mask. (c) Morphology-resolved EDS analysis is performed by pixel-wise intersection of each class mask with each elemental map, yielding the elemental signal attributable to each morphology class. The figure example illustrates the titanium case ($\text{Mask} \cap \text{Ti}$).

To demonstrate the practical application of our framework, we applied our trained segmentation model to 10 SEM images with corresponding EDS elemental maps associated with Ti, O, Al, Cl, N, and F elements; see Figure 6. The trained model rapidly segmented each image in less than one second, producing per-morphology masks (Flake, Sphere, and Other) that were then intersected pixel-wise with each EDS elemental map (according to Equation 5). Segmentation mask alignment with elemental signal boundaries (as shown in Figure 7) indicates that the predicted masks precisely align with the spatial extent of each morphological class for downstream compositional analysis.

Across the 10 test images, the pipeline identified a total of 718 particles, including 469 Flakes (86.4% of total segmented area), 72 Spheres (9.83%), and 177 Other particles (3.76%), as reported in Table 2. This particle-count breakdown is itself a meaningful result. In a typical material synthesis process aiming for

MXene flakes, the population of other morphologies (in this case, Sphere and Other) directly represents non-target products or impurities, which could be the unreacted precursors, oxidized phases, or side-reaction products. Our framework measures these populations at the individual-particle level, allowing for direct estimation of the synthesis yield, which cannot be determined by conventional field-averaged EDS or bulk characterization techniques. This meaningful information provides an overall image of the synthesis quality that is directly relevant to the material or device performance^{8,9}. In battery research, for example, impurity phases can act as electrochemically inactive sites, reduce ionic conductivity or introduce parasitic side reactions that hinder battery performance by reducing the energy density, or cycling stability^{3,23}.

The *within-morphology elemental composition* further reveals chemical identities of different classes; see Table 2, Figure 8a. It was found that Ti is the dominant element at 37.8% of within the Flake class, followed by O at 20.2% and N at 11.6%, consistent with the titanium carbide/nitride-based chemistry expected for MXene flakes⁷. In contrast, Sphere-class is enriched in O, Al, and F, suggesting an aluminum-rich oxide phase, which is likely the residual Al_2O_3 or $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ from incomplete MAX-phase etching during MXene synthesis²⁴. The Other class exhibits an intermediate and more fluorine-rich nature (F: 18.9%, O: 28.2%, Al: 16.6%), possibly the unreacted LiF precursor or residues such as AlF_3 ^{3,4}, NaAlF_6 ⁷. The *bulk quantification* (Figure 8b) confirmed the dominance of the Flake class populations and its primary Ti element (up to 98.6% of total Ti signal in the sample). In contrast, the Sphere class is the minority with about 10% of the total Al or F were found dominant in Sphere class. Overcoming the conventional field-averaged EDS, it is impossible to determine this quantification. The atomic-percent counterpart is shown in Supplementary Figure S5, with full atomic stoichiometries referenced to the least-abundant element in Supplementary Tables S8–S10.

Importantly, our framework goes beyond this first-level compositional identification. Typically, in a heterogeneous sample, the different morphologies often share a similar stoichiometry. They can propose a similar chemical composition but have adopted different shapes during the synthesis due to different growth kinetics, decomposition, or aggregation²⁵. Our SEMEX.Lab platform captures this meaningful information explicitly by pairwise elemental similarity across morphology classes (see Figure 9 and Supplementary Video 1). Finally, it can point out cases where distinct morphologies are compositionally comparable, efficiently guiding the user to deeply interpret their materials that could co-exist in multi-phase rather than distinct impurities. Critically, this similarity-based grouping represents a qualitative interpretive level beyond the statistical EDS provides.

Figure 7. Per-element EDS maps with overlaid morphology contours for a representative SEM. (a) Original SEM image. (b) Predicted segmentation mask with morphology classes: Flake (blue), Sphere (purple), and Other (orange). (c) Overlay of the segmentation mask on the original SEM image. (d–i) Elemental EDS maps overlaid with segmentation contours for Titanium (d), Aluminum (e), Oxygen (f), Fluorine (g), Nitrogen (h), and Chlorine (i).

Figure 8. Morphology-resolved elemental analysis across particle classes. Elemental statistics aggregated from 718 segmented particles across 10 SEM micrographs with co-acquired EDS elemental maps. (a) *Morphology class composition*. For each morphology class (Flake, Sphere, Other) the six element bars (Al, Cl, F, N, O, and Ti) sum to 100 %, revealing the stoichiometry of each particle type. (b) *Bulk composition*. For each element, the values what percentage of that element's total signal originates from Flakes, Spheres, and Other particles; the three morphology values sum to 100% per element. Numerical values are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Elemental composition resolved by particle morphology. Elemental statistics aggregated over 718 segmented particles from 10 SEM micrographs with co-acquired EDS elemental maps for Ti, O, Al, Cl, N, and F. *Morphology class composition (top)*: for each morphology class (Flake, Sphere, Other), the six element values sum to 100% and represent the relative elemental composition of that particle type across the six mapped elements. *Bulk composition (bottom)*: for each element, the values show what percentage of that element's total signal originates from Flakes, Spheres, and Other particles; rows sum to 100% per element. *N objects* = number of segmented particles per class; *Area fraction (%)* = fraction of total segmented particle area occupied by each class.

Morphology	N objects	Area fraction (%)	Ti	O	Al	Cl	N	F
Morphology class composition (%)								
Flake	469	86.4	37.8	20.2	10.2	14.6	11.6	5.6
Sphere	72	9.83	7.2	27.5	26.5	13.1	9.7	16.0
Other	177	3.76	11.2	28.2	16.6	13.5	11.6	18.9
Total	718	100.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
Bulk composition (%)								
Flake	—	—	98.6	91.9	87.3	94.5	94.6	83.8
Sphere	—	—	0.8	5.3	9.7	3.6	3.4	10.1
Other	—	—	0.6	2.8	3.1	1.9	2.0	6.1

MXene SEM - EDS Segmentation

Upload SEM image Run inference

✓ Image 32.jpeg

↓ CLICK AN ELEMENT TO ADD ITS EDS UPLOAD SLOT ON THE RIGHT

H																	He				
Li	Be															B	C	N	O	F	Ne
Na	Mg															Al	Si	P	S	Cl	Ar
K	Ca	Sc	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	As	Se	Br	Kr				
Rb	Sr	Y	Zr	Nb	Mo	Tc	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ag	Cd	In	Sn	Sb	Te	I	Xe				
Cs	Ba	La	Hf	Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Hg	Tl	Pb	Bi	Po	At	Rn				
Fr	Ra	Ac	Rf	Db	Sg	Bh	Hs	Mt	Ds	Rg	Cn	Nh	Fl	Mc	Lv	Ts	Og				
La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Pm	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu							
Ac	Th	Pa	U	Np	Pu	Am	Cm	Bk	Cf	Es	Fm	Md	No	Lr							

EDS IMAGES (CLICK ELEMENT FIRST)

Fluorine upload ✓ Image 32_analysis_1_map_F...

Oxygen upload ✓ Image 32_analysis_1_map_...

Nitrogen upload ✓ Image 32_analysis_1_map_...

Aluminum upload ✓ Image 32_analysis_1_map_A...

Chlorine upload ✓ Image 32_analysis_1_map_C...

Titanium upload ✓ Image 32_analysis_1_map_T...

SEM (FRONTP)

MASK OVERLAY ON SEM

EDS OVERLAY

MORPHOLOGY SIZE HISTOGRAM

EDS MORPHOLOGY COMPOSITION

EDS BULK COMPOSITION (STACKED)

RUN SUMMARY

Class #	Class	Objects	Area %	Dominant element	Stoichiometry	Similar to	Cosine sim. (± 0.55)
1	Flake	24	89.1%	Titanium (46.8%)	Ti3.6AlN3.104FC11.1	—	0.472
2	Sphere	6	8.1%	Aluminum (34.7%)	TiAl124.1N7.8028.1F27.1C12.9	Other	0.868
3	Other	12	2.8%	Fluorine (36.1%)	TiAl13.6N4015.9F15.7C11.3	Sphere	0.868

Device: CUDA - Inference size: 1024x1024 - Display crop: 30px/size - Stoichiometry excludes Carbon (substrate contamination)

Figure 9 SEMEX.Lab interactive interface for morphology-resolved SEM-EDS analysis. Representative screenshot of the deployable dashboard, illustrating the per-image analysis view applied to a single SEM-EDS acquisition.

3 Discussion

We have presented a lightweight, data-efficient framework for morphology-resolved SEM–EDS analysis. Training a 15 M-parameter UNet++ on five labeled MXene micrographs together with synthetic data generated by our canvas-based strategy, the model reaches an mIoU of 0.743 ± 0.003 with an inference time of ≈ 1.3 s per image on a standard CPU. Its three-class masks, intersected pixel-wise with co-acquired EDS maps, recover per-morphology compositional statistics inaccessible to field-averaged EDS.

The sufficiency of five labeled images, when extended by the canvas-based synthetic pipeline, is not specific to this dataset. It reflects a structural property of SEM micrographs that show discrete morphologies on a relatively uniform background. Object morphologies are position-invariant: a flake-shaped particle has the same geometric signature whether it lies in the corner or center of the field of view. A small instance pool, once extracted, can therefore be reused across thousands of synthetic placements. Backgrounds are sample- and instrument-specific, but within a single acquisition session they are statistically homogeneous. A 10×10 pixel mosaic tiled from real background regions therefore reproduces the correct distribution. Together, these properties let the pipeline compose new images, yielding a synthetic dataset whose pixel statistics match those of the source instrument and sample.

This design contrasts with two alternative strategies on SEM data augmentation. First, generative adversarial models such as the simulated-particle GAN²⁶ produce realistic SEM-like micrographs but require training a separate generator on a dedicated input dataset. Second, copy-paste augmentation²¹, by contrast, adds new objects to existing training images. The augmented image retains the background and overall scene composition of the original, so its object density and class ratio are fixed by the source. Our canvas-based strategy keeps the simplicity of copy-paste while producing fully synthetic images whose object density and class balance can be tuned independently of the synthetic dataset. In practice, this translates to roughly 2.5 hours of human annotation (the five training images at ~ 30 minutes each) and ~ 20 minutes of training on a single consumer GPU.

A direct consequence of the synthetic-data pipeline is improved segmentation of small and rare particles. The labeled morphology pool is dominated by flakes ($\sim 32:6:1$ for Flake:Sphere:Other), so small Sphere and Other morphologies have little training signal to be reliably segmented when the model is trained on real images alone. Sampling at a balanced 1:1:1 class ratio when constructing each synthetic image rebalances every training batch, lifting per-class IoU by +15.0 pp on Sphere and +29.5 pp on Other; see Table 1. This is achieved without any modification to the loss function or the model architecture: rebalancing happens entirely at the data-generation step and is therefore architecture-agnostic.

The choice of UNet++ with a ResNet-18 encoder reflects a deliberate prioritization of deployability over performance. The 15 M-parameter network runs in ≈ 1.3 s per image on CPU. The rare Other class plateaus near mIoU = 0.59, a direct consequence of the small instance pool — only 15 Other particles at $|D| = 5$. Enlarging the labeled set or substituting a heavier architecture (e.g. SAM^{27,28}) are both candidate remedies, but neither was pursued here because each conflict with our deplorability target. Although we opted for UNet++ here, the canvas-based pipeline operates entirely on data, not on the model, so it can be paired with any segmentation architecture without modification. Substituting a larger backbone is therefore a

straightforward extension, and the synthetic-data component becomes more valuable as models grow larger, and overfitting becomes a bigger concern.

These capabilities are surfaced through the SEMEX.Lab interface, which packages segmentation, mask-EDS intersection, and per-class composition reporting into a interface that requires no machine-learning expertise from the user. We further verified throughput on a bulk corpus of 2,589 unlabeled SEM images identifying over 360,000 particles in total (Supplementary Figure S6). This positions the framework as a deployable layer on top of existing instrumentation. However, several limitations should be noted. The framework is demonstrated on a single 2D energy-storage material acquired on a single instrument. Cross-instrument and cross-material generalization remains to be established, particularly for systems with strongly textured backgrounds or morphologies that violate our position-independence assumption (e.g., heavily clustered).

The pixel-wise intersection of segmentation masks with co-acquired EDS maps reveals compositional heterogeneity invisible to field-averaged analysis. The Flake class is Ti-dominant (37.8%) with moderate O (20.2%), consistent with $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene. Spheres are depleted in Ti (7.2%) and enriched in Al (26.5%), O (27.5%), and F (16.0%), pointing to Al-O based residuals, while the Other class shows elevated F (18.9%) suggestive of fluoride-based residues. Bulk partitioning confirms that 98.6% of the total Ti signal originates from Flakes, whereas Al and F are disproportionately concentrated in the minority populations that a distinction field-averaged EDS cannot make. Grouping materials by phase, the Sphere and Other classes share broadly similar stoichiometry, where both Ti-depleted and Al/O/F-enriched, leading to the question of whether they represent distinct phases or morphological variants of the same incompletely etched precursor observed by pairwise elemental similarity analysis in our SEMEX.Lab interface. This meaningful information could guide users toward targeted follow-up measurements such as X-ray diffraction (XRD). The EDS elemental maps used in this work represent raw X-ray intensity counts per pixel as acquired in imaging mode, and have not been subjected to ZAF correction; the reported compositional values should therefore be interpreted as semi-quantitative relative ratios rather than absolute atomic percentages.

The SEMEX.Lab UI (Figure 9) visualizes these MXene and impurity populations — countable and compositionally analyzed by class in one click. The SEMEX.Lab provides three levels of insight inaccessible to conventional SEM-EDS workflows: (i) morphological yield — the population-weighted fraction of the target phase by particle count and area; (ii) per-class elemental quantification — the intrinsic composition of each morphology, enabling phase identification and comparison to known reference compounds; and (iii) phase compositional similarity analysis — the grouping of morphologically distinct populations that share the same elemental identity, enabling the user to distinguish true phase diversity from morphological evolution. For high-throughput deployment, a complementary bulk-mode interface (Supplementary Figure S7) processes entire image folders in a single operation, returning the same per-class statistics aggregated across thousands of images — as demonstrated on a 2,589-image corpus comprising over 360,000 segmented particles

Ultimately, our framework, through SEMEX.Lab established a novel AI-driven characterization tool that directly addresses the bottlenecks of conventional SEM-EDS analysis, including manual operation, large annotation burden, and the lack of morphology-resolved EDS correlation. This work offers an AI-driven, CPU-deployable framework that links particle-level morphology to elemental composition across thousands of images in minutes, paving the way toward automated characterization and quality control in MXene and battery research, and broader high-value material or nanodevice manufacturing.

4 Method

4.1 Sample preparation and SEM-EDS acquisition

MXene titanium carbide material was synthesized from MAX phase (Ti_3AlC_2) according to the previous method²⁹. A Phenom XL G3 Desktop SEM equipped with EDS (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Cerium Hexaboride electron source) was used to collect SEM and EDS images in high-throughput mode, scanning the large sample area at a cm^2 scale. The sample was prepared by drop casting MXene suspension (in water) on a glassy carbon plate ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ area). The SEM images were taken using electron beam of 15 eV in Backscatter electron detector (BSD) mode, while EDS maps were collected using EDS instrument model MVE080522-10768-L, 20 kV electron beam.

4.2 Dataset and annotation

Datasets. A single high-throughput SEM acquisition run was performed on the MXene sample under the conditions described in *Section 4.1*, yielding 2,679 SEM images. From this single acquisition pool, three disjoint subsets were defined and used for distinct purposes throughout the study (*Table S11*):

Dataset 1 — Annotated SEM corpus (model development). Eighty SEM images were selected from the acquisition pool and annotated by two human experts using the Supervisely platform¹, requiring approximately 30 minutes per image. Each particle was annotated as one of three morphology classes: Flake, Sphere, or Other. Flakes are thin, sheet-like particles characteristic of MXene; spheres are round or near-spherical particles; and the Other class includes irregular fragments and structures that do not match either of the first two classes. Dataset 1 contained 12,486 annotated objects in total (11,290 Flakes, 984 Spheres, and 212 Others). Images were acquired at a native resolution of 1920×1275 pixels and resized to 1024×1024 pixels prior to training and inference. The 80 images were split into 10 training, 35 validation, and 35 test images. The training split was deliberately selected by selecting the 10 most representative images, mirroring the practical deployment scenario in which a user identifies a small set of images that best capture the morphological diversity of the sample for use with our synthetic data pipeline. Dataset 1 is the only dataset used for synthetic data generation (*Section 2.1*), model training (*Section 2.2*), and the ablation study of generation parameters (*Section 2.3*).

Dataset 2 — SEM-EDS pairs (morphology-resolved compositional analysis). Ten SEM images were drawn from the acquisition pool; for each image, co-acquired EDS elemental maps were collected for six elements (Ti, Al, O, F, Cl, N). EDS mapping was acquired only for this subset because of its substantially longer acquisition time per image compared with SEM imaging alone. These images carry no human-annotated segmentation masks. The masks here are obtained at inference time from the model trained on

¹ <https://supervisely.com> (accessed May 2026).

Dataset 1. Dataset 2 is used exclusively as a demonstration of morphology-resolved EDS analysis (*Section 2.4*) and is not used for any model training.

Dataset 3 — Bulk SEM corpus (deployment-scale demonstration). Dataset 3 consists of the remaining 2,589 SEM images from the acquisition pool, used to demonstrate the framework's throughput under realistic high-throughput conditions. These images carry neither human-annotated masks nor co-acquired EDS data. Like Dataset 2, segmentation masks are obtained at inference time from the model trained on Dataset 1. Dataset 3 is used solely to report aggregate, bulk-scale segmentation statistics, and is not used for any model training.

4.3 Synthetic data generation

The pipeline is illustrated in Figure 2b. From each annotated image in D , connected-component analysis is applied to the segmentation masks to extract individual particles, which are stored together with their binary masks in a per-class morphology pool. Particles with an area below 100 pixels are discarded to exclude annotation noise. At the default $|D| = 5$, this procedure yields a pool of 473 Flakes, 89 Spheres, and 15 Other particles.

The background of each synthetic image is constructed by mosaic tiling. For each synthetic image, one source image is randomly selected from D , and 10×10 pixel patches sampled from its background regions are tiled until a 1024×1024 canvas is filled. Particles are then sampled from the morphology pool and placed at uniformly random positions on the canvas. Sampling proportions are controlled by a configurable class ratio Flake:Sphere:Other, so that the per-image class distribution is independent of the pool size. Each particle is randomly rotated in 2D before placement; no scaling or photometric augmentation is applied. When particles overlap, they are layered with Flake at the bottom, Sphere in the middle, and Other on top, with the same ordering applied consistently to the image pixels and the segmentation mask. Placement continues until k particles have been pasted onto the canvas.

Default settings used throughout the paper, unless otherwise stated, are $|D| = 5$ real annotated images, $|D'| = 100$ synthetic images, $k = 120$ particles per synthetic image, and a Flake:Sphere:Other class ratio of 1:1:1.

4.4 Segmentation model architecture and training

We used UNet++²² with a ResNet-18³⁰ encoder pre-trained on ImageNet³¹, implemented in PyTorch. This architecture was chosen for its favorable accuracy-to-parameter trade-off, with approximately 15M parameters enabling CPU-deployable inference on standard SEM workstations without dedicated GPU hardware. The network was trained to segment four classes: Background, Flake, Sphere, and Other. Input images were resized to 1024×1024 pixels and normalized using ImageNet mean and standard deviation; the same deterministic preprocessing was applied to training, validation, and test splits. Random 2D rotation is incorporated at the morphology level during synthetic data generation (*Section 2.1*). Training used the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , batch size of 4. The loss function was standard cross-entropy without class weighting. Class balance was instead controlled by the 1:1:1 sampling ratio in the synthetic pipeline. A ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler halved the learning rate when validation loss failed to improve for two epochs. Training was terminated by early stopping with a patience of five epochs, up to

a maximum of 300 epochs. All models were trained on a single NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU; a typical run completed in approximately 20 minutes. Three random seeds (1, 52, 88) were used across all experiments for reproducibility. The complete training configuration is summarized in Table S3.

4.5 Evaluation metrics

Segmentation performance was quantified using the mean Intersection-over-Union (mIoU) and mean Dice coefficient, computed as the unweighted average of per-class IoU and Dice across all four classes (Background, Flake, Sphere, Other). For each class c , the per-class IoU and Dice are defined as

$$\mathbf{IoU}_c = \frac{\mathbf{TP}_c}{(\mathbf{TP}_c + \mathbf{FP}_c + \mathbf{FN}_c)} \quad 1$$

$$\mathbf{Dice}_c = \frac{\mathbf{TP}_c}{(2\mathbf{TP}_c + \mathbf{FP}_c + \mathbf{FN}_c)} \quad 2$$

where \mathbf{TP}_c , \mathbf{FP}_c , and \mathbf{FN}_c denote the number of true-positive, false-positive, and false-negative pixels for class c , respectively. The mean metrics are obtained by averaging across all four classes:

$$\mathbf{mIoU} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \mathbf{IoU}_c \quad 3$$

$$\mathbf{Dice} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1}^C \mathbf{Dice}_c \quad 4$$

with $C = 4$. Background was included in the mean to reflect overall pixel-level segmentation quality. All metrics were computed on the held-out test set of 35 images (4,865 annotated objects) and are reported as mean \pm standard deviation across three independent training runs with three random seeds.

4.6 Morphology-resolved EDS analysis

To obtain elemental statistics resolved by particle morphology, the segmentation masks predicted by the trained model M_{seg} were combined with co-acquired EDS elemental maps through pixel-wise intersection; see Figure 6. EDS maps for six elements (Ti, Al, O, F, Cl, and N) were acquired simultaneously with 10 selected SEM images. Each EDS map E_e is a 2D image whose pixel value reports the X-ray intensity for element e . For each SEM image, the image itself and its co-acquired EDS maps were resampled to a common 1024×1024 pixel to ensure pixel-level alignment.

The resampled SEM image was passed through M_{seg} to obtain a semantic mask assigning every pixel to one of three morphology classes. For each morphology class $c \in \{Flake, Sphere, Other\}$ and each element e , the EDS signal attributable to that morphology was obtained by pixel-wise intersection of the binary class mask Ω_c with the elemental intensity map E_e :

$$\mathbf{I}_{c,e} = \Omega_c \cap E_e \quad 5$$

where \cap denotes pixel-wise multiplication, Ω_c is the binary mask of class c , and $I_{c,e}$ is the resulting intensity image of element e restricted to pixels assigned to class c . The total X-ray intensity of element e attributable to class c is then obtained by summing over all pixels:

$$S_{c,e} = \sum I_{c,e} \quad 6$$

From the per-class intensities, two complementary views were derived:

Morphology class composition (Figure 8a). For each morphology class c , the relative contribution of element e is

$$f_{c,e}^{class} = \frac{S_{c,e}}{\sum_{e'} S_{c,e'}} \times 100 \% \quad 7$$

where the sum in the denominator runs over all six elements, so that the six element fractions sum to 100 % within each class. This view characterizes the elemental composition of each particle type.

Bulk composition (Figure 8b). For each element e , the fractional contribution of morphology class c to the total signal is

$$f_{c,e}^{bulk} = \frac{S_{c,e}}{\sum_{c'} S_{c',e}} \times 100 \% \quad 8$$

where the sum in the denominator runs over all three morphologies, so that the three morphology fractions sum to 100 % per element. This view splits the bulk EDS signal of each element into contributions from each morphology class.

Particle-level statistics — number of objects per class and the image area fraction occupied by each class — were obtained from connected-component analysis of the predicted masks. The values reported in Fig. 8 and Table 2 are relative EDS intensity fractions computed directly from raw X-ray intensity maps without ZAF correction and should therefore be interpreted as semi-quantitative compositional ratios rather than absolute atomic percentages.

The same procedure can be applied to arbitrarily large SEM–EDS image sets without modification; the per-image inference time of ~ 1.3 seconds on CPU (~ 35 ms on GPU) makes the analysis practical for high-throughput SEM datasets.

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7 Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors assert that they have no conflicts of interest or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

8 Reference

- 1 Gogotsi, Y. & Anasori, B. The Rise of MXenes. *ACS Nano* **13**, 8491-8494 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.9b06394>
- 2 The pull of the MXene vortex. *Nature Nanotechnology* **17**, 1025-1025 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-022-01238-6>
- 3 Cockreham, C. B. *et al.* Inhibition of $AlF_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ Impurity Formation in Ti_3C_2Tx MXene Synthesis under a Unique $CoFx/HCl$ Etching Environment. *ACS Applied Energy Materials* **2**, 8145-8152 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.9b01618>
- 4 Rakhi, R. B., Ahmed, B., Hedhili, M. N., Anjum, D. H. & Alshareef, H. N. Effect of Postetch Annealing Gas Composition on the Structural and Electrochemical Properties of Ti_2CTx MXene Electrodes for Supercapacitor Applications. *Chemistry of Materials* **27**, 5314-5323 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.5b01623>
- 5 Zhang, X. *et al.* Hierarchical NiFeP Nanoflowers on the MXene Film as a Self-Standing Bifunctional Electrode toward Superior Overall Water Electrolysis. *ACS Applied Nano Materials* **7**, 7684-7693 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.4c00379>
- 6 Li, L., Mao, L. & Yang, J. A Review of Principles, Analytical Methods, and Applications of SEM-EDS in Cementitious Materials Characterization. *Advanced Materials Technologies* **10**, 2401175 (2025). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202401175>
- 7 Chae, Y. *et al.* Scalable synthesis of high-purity Ti_4N_3Tx MXene via saturated salt solution (S3) etching. *Advanced Powder Materials* **4**, 100334 (2025). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmate.2025.100334>
- 8 Qureshi, N., Choi, C.-H. & Doh, J. Expediting High-Yield Mxene Carbides and Nitrides Synthesis for Next-Generation 2D Materials. *Advanced Materials Technologies* **9**, 2301611 (2024). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202301611>
- 9 Jolly, S., Paranthaman, M. P. & Naguib, M. Synthesis of Ti_3C_2Tz MXene from low-cost and environmentally friendly precursors. *Materials Today Advances* **10**, 100139 (2021). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtadv.2021.100139>

- 10 Gopinath, S. C. B. *et al.* Failure analysis on silicon semiconductor device materials: optical and high-resolution microscopic assessments. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* **21**, 3451-3461 (2022). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.10.116>
- 11 Azimi, S. M., Britz, D., Engstler, M., Fritz, M. & Mücklich, F. Advanced Steel Microstructural Classification by Deep Learning Methods. *Scientific Reports* **8**, 2128 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-20037-5>
- 12 Tsutsui, K. *et al.* A methodology of steel microstructure recognition using SEM images by machine learning based on textural analysis. *Materials Today Communications* **25**, 101514 (2020). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2020.101514>
- 13 Durmaz, A. R. *et al.* A deep learning approach for complex microstructure inference. *Nature Communications* **12**, 6272 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26565-5>
- 14 Rettenberger, L. *et al.* Uncertainty-aware particle segmentation for electron microscopy at varied length scales. *npj Computational Materials* **10**, 124 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-024-01302-w>
- 15 Rettenberger, L. *et al.* Leveraging unlabeled SEM datasets with self-supervised learning for enhanced particle segmentation. *npj Computational Materials* **11**, 289 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-025-01802-3>
- 16 Lyu, Z., Yao, L., Chen, W., Kalutantirige, F. C. & Chen, Q. Electron Microscopy Studies of Soft Nanomaterials. *Chemical Reviews* **123**, 4051-4145 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.2c00461>
- 17 Schmidt, U., Weigert, M., Broaddus, C. & Myers, G. in *Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2018*. (eds Alejandro F. Frangi *et al.*) 265-273 (Springer International Publishing).
- 18 Zhang, Y. *et al.* in *2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. 10140-10150.
- 19 Bals, J. & Epple, M. Artificial Scanning Electron Microscopy Images Created by Generative Adversarial Networks from Simulated Particle Assemblies. *Advanced Intelligent Systems* **5**, 2300004 (2023). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/aisy.202300004>
- 20 Dwibedi, D., Misra, I. & Hebert, M. in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*. 1310-1319.
- 21 Ghiasi, G. *et al.* in *2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. 2917-2927.
- 22 Zhou, Z., Siddiquee, M. M. R., Tajbakhsh, N. & Liang, J. UNet++: A Nested U-Net Architecture for Medical Image Segmentation. *Deep Learn Med Image Anal Multimodal Learn Clin Decis Support (2018)* **11045**, 3-11 (2018). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00889-5_1
- 23 Alam, S. *et al.* Recent advancements in the performance of MXene and its various composites as an electrode material in asymmetric supercapacitors. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* **961**, 171007 (2023). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2023.171007>
- 24 Saeedi, F., Zare, E., Ansari, R., Haghgoo, M. & Sahmani, S. MXenes: Bridging the Gap Between Advanced Materials and Sustainable Technologies in Energy and Environmental Applications. *Advanced Electronic Materials* **12**, e00801 (2026). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/aelm.202500801>
- 25 Yang, H. *et al.* Catalytic Performance for the Conversion of Potent Fluorinated Greenhouse Gases by Aluminium Fluorides with Different Morphology. *Catalysis Letters* **151**, 2065-2074 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10562-020-03446-y>
- 26 Goodfellow, I. *et al.* Generative adversarial networks. *Commun. ACM* **63**, 139-144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3422622>
- 27 Ravi, N. *et al.* in *International Conference on Learning Representations*. 28085-28128.
- 28 Kirillov, A. *et al.* in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*. 4015-4026.

- 29 Chunlim, H. *et al.* Solution-processed, binder-free pristine Ti₃C₂T_x MXene electrodes enabled by MAI passivation for high-performance, scalable perovskite solar cells. *Applied Surface Science Advances* **28**, 100803 (2025).
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsadv.2025.100803>
- 30 He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S. & Sun, J. in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 770-778.
- 31 Deng, J. *et al.* in *2009 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 248-255 (Ieee).

9 Author Contribution

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Kajjana Boonpalit; Data preparation and annotation.

Kanakorn Suk-ieam; Literature and data visualization

Visarut Nganpipatmongkon; Material synthesis.

Pasit Pakawatpanurut; Resources, investigation, review & editing, and grant acquisition.

Antonella Badia; Resources, investigation, review & editing, and grant acquisition.

Takayuki Okatani; Resources, method, investigation, review & editing, supervision, and grant acquisition.

Siraprapha Deebansok; Conceptualization, method, investigation, data collection, visualization, writing original draft, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition.